

Report

Scientific study on the validity, reliability and repeatability of two visual scoring methods of assessment of the litter quality

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1 Executive Summary

The visual assessment of the litter quality in broiler chickens, valuable indicator of birds welfare, is commonly used in scientific studies or on-field in broiler chickens barns. Visual assessment of litter quality is highly feasible but it may be considered as subjective, depending on the assessor and not reflecting the evolution of physical parameters such as the litter moisture. This study aimed to evaluate the validity, the reliability between several assessors and the repeatability for a same assessor of three visual scores from the Welfare Quality (one score) and the Classyfarm protocols (two complementary scores: Friability and Humidity scores).

2 Introduction

The litter in poultry production is characterized by the mixture of bedding materials, feathers, birds faeces, and feed or water spilled during rearing (Brink et al., 2022). The litter could vary in type (wood shavings, straw, coarse sawdust, etc.) or depth. Maintaining high-quality litter (meaning dry and friable) is a primary objective in the management of poultry houses, as poor-quality litter could have significant consequences on the health and welfare of birds. A good litter quality provides insulation and cushioning for the birds from the floor, contributing to their comfort by keeping them dry (Collett, 2012). A dry and friable litter is also essential for the birds' welfare, enabling the expression of natural behaviours such as scratching, foraging or dust bathing (Welfare Quality®, 2009). Conversely, soiled litter can have negative consequences on birds' health and welfare. For example, wet litter is known to increase the incidence of footpad dermatitis in poultry (Shepherd and Fairchild, 2010; Shepherd et al., 2017). Wet and/or caked litter also impairs the realisation of comfort, exploration and foraging behaviours by the chickens (EFSA, 2023). Additionally, the quality of the litter is directly linked to ammonia volatilization (NH_3), a major hazard on poultry farms that affects animal health. Several studies have highlighted the importance of litter moisture on the microbial growth of nitrifying bacteria, leading to the production of NH_3 (Miles et al., 2011; Toppel et al., 2019). High NH_3 concentrations can lead to birds' eyes lesions such as uveitis or keratoconjunctivitis, respiratory issues, and severe pathological damage or infections (Miles et al., 2004; David et al., 2015; Cohuo-Colli et al., 2018).

As poor litter quality is a risk factor for health and welfare of chickens, assessing litter moisture can be considered as a proxy to monitor them, in particular during on-farm inspections. It can be done through various instrumental methods (portable instruments on field or measuring litter moisture of samples in laboratory) requiring time for analyses and/or specific expensive equipment, that also need appropriate calibration. In contrast, visual assessment can be conducted without any instruments, is instantaneous, and easily feasible. Visual assessment is generally performed in various litter areas in the barn to capture the variability of litter quality. For example, in proximity to the drinker line, spillage of drinking water by the birds may result in a more humid litter. Similarly, the traffic near the drinkers and feeders area could lead to a greater accumulation of excreta in the litter. In the opposite, an area close to a wall and away from feeders and drinkers, may have a more friable and dry litter (Brink et al., 2022). The visual scoring system mostly used in poultry studies comes from the Welfare Quality Protocol©(2009), a project that had developed standardized ways of assessing on-farm welfare of several species. Other welfare assessment protocols had developed litter quality evaluation scale such as the Classyfarm Protocol with two separated sub-scales (IZSLER, 2023): one aiming to score the friability, the other scoring the humidity of litter.

However, visual scoring system may be considered as a subjective method that requires a validation of its results before being considered as a trustworthy method to assess the litter quality in poultry barns. Furthermore, it is crucial to ensure that the evaluation grids allow for inter-assessors' reliability and intra-assessor repeatability. The inter-assessor reliability reflects the variation between two or more assessors who measure the same variable, whereas the intra-

assessor repeatability reflects the variation of data measured by one assessor across two or more trials (Koo and Li, 2016). To the authors' knowledge, neither the validity nor the reliability and repeatability of the Welfare Quality visual scoring system had been assessed in previous studies. While the validity of the Classyfarm visual scoring system has already been explored in turkey farms (Vinco et al., 2018), the reliability and repeatability of this visual scoring system had not been studied yet.

The present study aimed to assess the validity, inter-assessor reliability and intra-assessor repeatability of three litter quality scoring scales in broiler chickens farms: one score from the Welfare Quality protocol (Welfare Quality®, 2009) and two from the Classyfarm Protocol (IZSLER, 2023). First, to assess the validity of these visual scoring systems, litter moisture (considered here as the main indicator of litter quality) was compared with each visual score in various areas of an experimental barn. In the second part, the inter-assessor reliability of these visual scoring systems among four assessors and the intra-assessor repeatability between two successive assessments conducted by each assessor were analysed. To achieve this goal, assessments were conducted by multiple assessors across different stages of litter degradation (two different time points along the broiler chickens production cycle) and in various areas of an experimental barn. This approach was intended to get a high variability of litter samples needed to study deeply the validity, reliability and repeatability of the visual scoring systems depending on the litter moisture level.

3 Materials and Methods

The present study was carried out in six experimental rooms of 162 m². In each room, 2450 medium-growing strain (REDBRO) broiler chickens were reared on litter composed of 1.2 kg/m² of coarse sawdust on concrete floor, until 43 days of age, an average body weight of 2.2 kg and final stocking density of 33 kg/m². The litter was not renewed during all the rearing period. The rooms differed on the composition and quantity of enrichment material provided since the experiment was also used to study the impacts of enrichments on broiler chicken behaviour (Guinebretière et al., 2024). Therefore, three rooms contained an elevated platform, two pecking blocks and two straw bales (E rooms) and in three other rooms, a higher elevated platform, four perches, five panels, four straw bales, four pecking blocks, a dustbathing container, three food pecking distributors and an 18 m² area in the room (not delimited physically) covered with a different litter of wood shavings (EC rooms).

Four assessors conducted visual litter quality assessments at two different time points during the broiler chickens' production cycle, on day 29 and day 36 (referred to as D29 and D36, respectively). Quantitative assessments were also carried out at D29 and D36. The litter assessments on D29 and D36 were chosen to avoid extremes in litter quality, ensuring that the litter was already used by the birds but not excessively soiled, as might occur during the final days of the rearing period. The method of the assessments consisted in evaluating litter quality in 1 m² of five distinct areas in both E and EC rooms. The five areas were between feeders, under

the drinker line, close to a wall, in an exploration area close to a straw bale and in the middle of the pen. Additionally, litter samples were evaluated in the 18 m² area of litter shavings in the three EC rooms. Thus, a total of 33 areas were assessed in D29 and D36.

Visual assessment

Each area previously mentioned was visually assessed on the same day two successive times (spaced out one hour apart, without communicating with each other or referring to their previous assessments) by every assessor to assess the intra-assessor repeatability between both successive assessments, at D29 and D36, and scored using three different qualitative scales.

The first scoring was based on the litter quality assessment method from the Welfare quality protocol (Welfare Quality®, 2009) and the second one, the Classyfarm Protocol that is used by Italian official inspectors in poultry farms (IZSLER, 2023) that consists in two different but complementary assessments: friability score and humidity score.

The five-class scale from the Welfare Quality protocol goes from score 0 to 4: score 0= completely dry and flaky, score 1= dry, but not easy to move with foot, score 2= leaves imprint of foot and will form a ball if compacted, but ball does not stay together well, score 3= sticks to boots and sticks readily in ball if compacted, score 4= sticks to boots once the cap or compacted crust is broken (Welfare Quality®, 2009). A high score corresponds then to a sticky and caked litter.

On the other hand, the Classyfarm Protocol (IZSLER, 2023) for litter quality assessment combines two visual sub-scores: one score describing the friability of the litter and, one score the humidity. Both sub-scores are ten-class scale and are described in Table 1: Description of the visual scores for friability and wetness of the Classyfarm protocol (Vinco et al., 2018; IZSLER, 2023) Here, high scores of friability and humidity correspond to a dry and friable litter and thus, on opposite scale in relation to the Welfare Quality protocol.

Table 1: Description of the visual scores for friability and wetness of the Classyfarm protocol (Vinco et al., 2018; IZSLER, 2023)

Score	Friability Description	Humidity Description
1	Completely caked	Wet litter, water is appearing by pressure on the litter of the total area
2	80-90 % area caked	Wet litter, water is appearing by pressure on the litter beneath drinkers
3	70-80 % area caked	Wet litter, no water is appearing by pressure on the litter
4	60-70 % area caked	Wet litter dark coloured, Litter can be pressed into ball-shape
5	50-60 % area caked	Wet litter, dark coloured, Larger ridges beneath drinkers

6	40 % area caked	Almost dry litter, small ridges beneath drinkers, Litter between drinkers and feeders is still friable
7	30 % area caked	Almost dry litter, dark coloured beneath drinkers and in other areas light coloured, ridge formation just started beneath drinkers
8	10 % area caked	Almost dry litter, light coloured, no ridges beneath drinkers
9	Friable litter, small caked areas	Dry litter, light coloured
10	Friable litter, no caked areas	Very dry litter (only observed at start)

Quantitative assessment (litter moisture)

Litter samples were collected to assess the litter moisture in every area (n = 33) on D29 and D36. Approximately two handfuls of litter (around 10 cm diameter on the ground) were collected in a plastic bag per area (one sample per area). Each sample was manually mixed and a subsample of approximately 20cL of litter were then weighed, dried for 24 h at 70°C and reweighed to measure indirectly the litter moisture (McLean et al., 2002). This difference determines the amount of wetness lost during the drying and the result was expressed as a percentage.

Statistical analysis

Data pre-processing and statistical analyses were analysed using R software v. 4.0.3 and RStudio (R Core Team, 2023).

In order to assess the impact of litter moisture levels on the results of validity, inter-assessor reliability and intra-assessor repeatability, correlations were analysed based on various moisture thresholds. Following the distribution of the litter moisture data, Spearman's rank correlations between assessors' scores and the litter moisture were conducted separately for samples with moisture levels below 30%, between 30 and 35%, between 35 and 40%, between 40 and 45%, and above 45%. The correlations within these different groups were then compared using Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney tests, revealing a significant difference at 35% of moisture. Consequently, this threshold was kept to investigate validity, inter-assessor reliability, and intra-assessor repeatability depending on litter moisture below 35% (concerning 28 samples) or above (concerning 38 samples).

Validity of each scoring system was assessed by means of a correlation analysis between the litter moisture (continuous variable) and the visual scores (ordinal variables computed as continuous variables) of all assessors, regrouped, using Spearman's rank correlations. The strength of the correlations was analysed according to the correlation coefficient (r) as follows: **weak** when $r < 0.30$; **moderate**: when r was between 0.30 and 0.50 and, **strong** when $r > 0.50$.

The inter-assessor reliability among assessors for each scoring scales was assessed using the Intra-Class Correlations (ICC). The ICC is a widely used reliability index in inter-rater reliability analysis (Koo and Li, 2016) where rating scale is continuous or ordinal. Following Koo and Li guideline (2016), the ICC value can be interpreted as follows: **poor reliability**: <0.50 ; **moderate reliability**: 0.50 to 0.75 ; **good reliability**: 0.75 to 0.90 ; **excellent reliability**: >0.90 . The ICC analysis giving only an expected value of the true ICC, the level of reliability is more related to its 95% confidence interval. This confidence interval indicates that there is 95% chance that the true ICC value lands on any point between the lower and the upper bounds (Koo and Li, 2016). This confidence interval will carry significant consideration in the present study.

Intra-assessor repeatability of the three scores was assessed using the Cohen's weighted Kappa (κ) for two raters. This is an index of interrater agreement between two assessors on ordinal data. In the present study, it was not used to assess the interrater agreement but the agreement between two assessments of a same assessor. As a rating scale, the Cohen's weighted Kappa allows for the consideration of various degrees of disagreement, not limited to a simple agreement/disagreement. In our analysis, the weighted Kappa coefficient with "squared" weights was chosen; in this way, disagreements between two successive assessments were weighted according to their squared distance from perfect agreement. Thus, squared weights assign more importance to major disagreements than minor disagreements. The value of weighted Kappa expresses the degree to which the proportion of agreement among assessors exceeds what would be expected if all assessors made their assessments completely randomly. It ranges from -1 to $+1$, where 0 indicates the amount of agreement that can be expected from random chance, and 1 represents perfect agreement between assessments. The widely accepted conventional interpretation of the Cohen's Kappa within the scientific community: **poor** when $\kappa < 0$; **slight** when $0 < \kappa < 0.20$, **fair** when $0.21 < \kappa < 0.40$; **moderate** when $0.41 < \kappa < 0.60$; **substantial** when $0.61 < \kappa < 0.80$ and, **almost perfect** when $0.81 < \kappa < 1$ (Landis, 1977).

4 Results

Validity: correlations between scoring scales and litter moisture

The results showed that the correlations (all significant, $p < 0.001$) between the visual scoring scales and the quantitative determination of the litter moisture were different when the litter moisture was below or above 35%. Below 35% of litter moisture, whether with both Classyfarm visual scores or with the Welfare Quality score, the correlations with litter moisture were moderate ($r = -0.43$ for Classyfarm Friability score; $r = -0.48$ for Classyfarm Humidity score; $r = 0.47$ for Welfare Quality score) (Figure 1: Scatter plot and correlations between Classyfarm scoring scales and litter moisture when the litter moisture is below 35% (A) and above 35% (B) (all 4 assessors considered). Classyfarm ranges from 1 to 10, 10 being very dry litter. A and Figure 2: Scatter plot and correlations between Welfare Quality scoring scale and litter moisture when the litter moisture is below 35% (A) and above 35% (B) (all 4 assessors considered) Welfare Quality scoring ranges from 0 to 4, 0 being very dry litter. A). In contrast, correlations between visual scoring scales and

litter moisture were strong when the litter moisture was above 35% ($r=-0.77$ for Classyfarm Friability score; $r=-0.72$ for Classyfarm Humidity score; $r=0.73$ for Welfare Quality score) (Figure 1: Scatter plot and correlations between Classyfarm scoring scales and litter moisture when the litter moisture is below 35% (A) and above 35% (B) (all 4 assessors considered). Classyfarm ranges from 1 to 10, 10 being very dry litter.B and Figure 2: Scatter plot and correlations between Welfare Quality scoring scale and litter moisture when the litter moisture is below 35% (A) and above 35% (B) (all 4 assessors considered) Welfare Quality scoring ranges from 0 to 4, 0 being very dry litter.B).

Figure 1: Scatter plot and correlations between Classyfarm scoring scales and litter moisture when the litter moisture is below 35% (A) and above 35% (B) (all 4 assessors considered). Classyfarm ranges from 1 to 10, 10 being very dry litter.

Figure 2: Scatter plot and correlations between Welfare Quality scoring scale and litter moisture when the litter moisture is below 35% (A) and above 35% (B) (all 4 assessors considered) Welfare Quality scoring ranges from 0 to 4, 0 being very dry litter.

Reliability of the scoring scales

Similarly, the reliability differed according to the litter moisture level. Below 35%, the reliability, according to the ICC value, was good for the Classyfarm Friability score and moderate for the Classyfarm Humidity and Welfare Quality scores (Table 2: Inter-assessor reliability for each visual scoring scales according to the litter moisture (ICC calculation using 2-way random effect model and absolute agreement) (4 assessors considered)). Above 35% of litter moisture, the reliability of the Classyfarm Friability and Welfare Quality scores was excellent whereas it was good for the Classyfarm Humidity score.

Table 2: Inter-assessor reliability for each visual scoring scales according to the litter moisture (ICC calculation using 2-way random effect model and absolute agreement) (4 assessors considered)

LITTER MOISTURE	SCORE	INTRA-CLASS CORRELATION	95% CONFIDENCE INTERVAL		P-VALUE
			LOWER BOUND	UPPER BOUND	
LOWER (<35%)	Classyfarm Friability	0.83	0.70	0.92	<0.001
	Classyfarm Humidity	0.71	0.49	0.85	<0.001
	Welfare Quality	0.72	0.42	0.87	<0.001

HIGHER (>35%)	Classyfarm Friability	0.96	<i>0.93</i>	<i>0.98</i>	<0.001
	Classyfarm Humidity	0.90	<i>0.83</i>	<i>0.94</i>	<0.001
	Welfare Quality	0.91	<i>0.84</i>	<i>0.95</i>	<0.001

Repeatability of the scoring scales

As for validity and reliability results, the repeatability varied when the litter moisture was below or above 35% (Table 3: Number of assessors (out of four) in each Cohen's Weighted Kappa category (Landis and Koch, 1977) for intra-assessor repeatability scores between successive assessments, when litter moisture is below or above 35%, "NS" indicate non-significant results ($p>0.05$)). When litter moisture was below 35%, the repeatability of the Classyfarm Friability score was substantial to almost perfect for three out of four assessors, while one assessor showed moderate repeatability. Similarly, three out of four assessors demonstrated substantial repeatability for the Welfare Quality score, with one assessor having moderate repeatability. However, for the Classyfarm Humidity score, three out of four assessors exhibited moderate repeatability when litter moisture was below 35%. When litter moisture exceeded 35%, all four assessors achieved substantial to almost perfect repeatability with the Classyfarm Friability and Welfare Quality scores. For the Classyfarm Humidity score, three assessors maintained substantial to almost perfect repeatability, while one assessor showed moderate repeatability.

Table 3: Number of assessors (out of four) in each Cohen's Weighted Kappa category (Landis and Koch, 1977) for intra-assessor repeatability scores between successive assessments, when litter moisture is below or above 35%, "NS" indicate non-significant results ($p>0.05$)

Kappa value	Classyfarm Friability		Classyfarm Humidity		Welfare Quality	
	<35% moisture	>35% moisture	<35% moisture	>35% moisture	<35% moisture	>35% moisture
Almost perfect (0.81-1)	1/4	3/4		2/4		3/4
Substantial (0.61-0.80)	2/4	1/4		1/4	3/4	1/4
Moderate (0.41-0.60)	1/4		3/4	1/4	1/4	
Fair (0.21-0.40)						
Slight (0-0.20)						
Poor (<0)						
NS			1/4			

5 Discussion

Validity: correlations between scoring scales and litter moisture

The Welfare Quality score and both Classyfarm scores were correlated with litter moisture: moderately when litter moisture was lower (under 35%) and strongly when it was higher (above 35%). Both visual scoring systems are valid indicators to reflect the wetness of the litter, which is known to affect negatively the welfare of chickens, by being a risk factor for skin lesions such as footpad dermatitis or hock burns (Haslam et al., 2007). The Classyfarm and Welfare Quality scores enable assessors to provide an accurate overview of the moisture level in the litter, especially when it exceeds 35% (considered as wet litter (Sargeant et al., 2019)), visual scores reflecting the impact that moisture has on litter appearance. No previous study investigated the correlation between the Welfare Quality score and the effective litter moisture. Vinco et al. (2018) compared the Classyfarm scoring scales and other moisture assessment methods in turkeys barns including the method used in this study (litter weighted before and after drying). They showed that the correlation between Classyfarm Scores and litter moisture evaluated with this method was only moderate ($0.30 < r < 0.50$). The present study was conducted on broiler chickens reared in an experimental facility, whereas Vinco's study assessed litter in turkey commercial farms, this could partly explain the difference. In our study, the litter was thin, and not aged of more than 36 days while in Vinco's study, the farms were inspected at the end of the turkey production cycle (135-140 days of age), likely resulting in a thicker accumulated litter. Therefore, as hypothesised by Vinco et al. (2018), the weighing evaluation of wet and dry litter assessed the overall water content of the litter, whereas the visual scoring only evaluates the surface layer of the litter. In contrast, in our study, as the litter was thin, the litter sample weighted (quantitative method) reflected better the litter layer visually scored, increasing probably the strength of our correlation between both methods. Furthermore, in Vinco's study, while samples with varying levels of litter moisture were examined, the correlations between the two methods were not analysed based on different levels of litter moisture. The present study's results have shown the role of the litter moisture level, in particular below and above 35%, in the strength of the correlations between litter moisture and visual scores.

Reliability of the scoring scales

The inter-assessor reliability of the three scoring scales was better when the litter moisture was higher than 35% in comparison with a litter moisture below 35%. Nevertheless, when litter moisture was below 35%, the reliability of the Classyfarm Friability score was considered good, outperforming the Classyfarm Humidity and Welfare Quality scores, which exhibited only moderate reliability. Examining the 95% Confidence Interval (95% CI), the results also indicated better reliability for the Classyfarm Friability score, ranging from moderate to excellent, whereas the reliability for the other two scores was rated from poor to good.

When the litter moisture exceeded 35%, the Classyfarm Friability score once again demonstrated the highest inter-assessor reliability, matching the excellent reliability observed in the Welfare Quality score. The Classyfarm Humidity score exhibited 'only' good reliability but, in reality, differed by just 0.01 ICC points compared to the Welfare Quality score, indicating similar reliability.

Both the Classyfarm Humidity and Welfare Quality scores had good to excellent reliability according to the 95% CI, whereas the Classyfarm Friability score demonstrated excellent reliability. This confirms that, even though the reliability of all scores improved with higher litter moisture, the Classyfarm Friability score consistently exhibited better reliability than the other two visual scoring scales.

Repeatability of the scoring scales

Similarly, the intra-assessor repeatability of the three scores was better when the litter moisture was higher than 35%. When the litter moisture was below 35%, the Classyfarm Friability score and the Welfare Quality score were similar, with the Classyfarm Friability score showing slightly higher repeatability (one assessor had almost perfect repeatability). In contrast, the Classyfarm Humidity score was less repeatable. When the moisture exceeded 35%, the Classyfarm Friability and Welfare Quality scores had the same high repeatability, almost perfect for three out of four assessors and substantial for the remaining one. The repeatability of the Classyfarm Humidity score was good above 35% moisture, with three out of four assessors achieving substantial to almost perfect repeatability and one achieving moderate repeatability. Regardless of the litter moisture, the Classyfarm Friability and Welfare Quality scores demonstrated better repeatability than the Classyfarm Humidity score.

6 Conclusions and Recommendations from EURCAW Poultry-SFA

This study has shown that **visual scoring systems are best suited for assessing litter samples with a moisture level above 35%**, as their validity, inter-assessor reliability, and intra-assessor repeatability were higher in this instance. Below 35% litter moisture, the results were more mixed. **All three scoring scales exhibited moderate validity at moisture levels below 35% and strong validity above 35%.** However, **the Classyfarm Friability score was the most reliable scoring scale regardless of litter moisture. Regarding intra-assessor repeatability, the Classyfarm Friability and Welfare Quality scores outperformed the Classyfarm Humidity score.**

The Classyfarm protocol for litter assessment was intended to use both friability and humidity scores. However, as revealed in this study, the two scores exhibited unequal inter-assessor reliability and intra-assessor repeatability. Simplifying the litter assessment in the Classyfarm Protocol by retaining only the friability score may be advisable, as it was more reliable and repeatable compared to the Classyfarm Humidity score. Furthermore, although the Welfare Quality score had similar validity and repeatability, it appeared to be less reliable than the

Classyfarm Friability score. Therefore, it is recommended to prioritize the use of the Classyfarm Friability score, particularly when comparing scores from multiple assessors.

The variability in validity, reliability, and repeatability results across different litter moisture levels suggests that **assessors exhibit greater consistency when evaluating lower-quality litter**. This underscores **the importance of exercising caution when visually assessing lightly degraded litter**. Finally, considering the diverse litter materials and depths used in poultry farming, further studies in varying litter conditions may validate these findings obtained from scoring systems used on thin layers of coarse sawdust.

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About EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is one of the four European Union Reference Centres for Animal Welfare. It focuses on poultry and other small farmed animals welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from hatch/birth to the end of life. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's main objective is to scientifically and technically support the European Commission and Member States for implementation of welfare legislation. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 1999/74/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens;
- Directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production.

Partners

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA receives funding from DG SANTE of the European Commission and represents a collaboration between the following four partner institutions:

- ANSES, France
- IRTA, Spain
- ANIVET, AU, Denmark
- IZSLER, Italy

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Activities of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Good Practices
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource-based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics, identify research needs and perform scientific and technical studies to fill the gaps of knowledge;
- Training
Reviewing existing training activities and developing new training materials, webinars and knowledge pills for official inspectors and competent authorities;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, and newsletter.

Website and contact

EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of poultry and other small farmed animals' welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of poultry and other small farmed animals welfare in the EU. For more information go to the Q2E webform available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/Queryw>. All Q2E answers are available [online](#).